

Words: Types, Knowledge, Learning, and Testing

Alireza Barouni Ebrahimi

University of Western Ontario, Canada

Abstract

This article explores the multifaceted nature of vocabulary knowledge, focusing on different vocabulary types, the processes involved in acquiring this knowledge, and the methods used to assess it. By examining deliberate and incidental learning approaches, the article highlights the importance of balancing structured vocabulary instruction with opportunities for spontaneous acquisition. Key strategies for vocabulary learning, such as the use of graded readers and flashcards, are discussed, along with the role of technology in supporting these practices. The article also provides an in-depth analysis of vocabulary testing, detailing various test formats and their applications, including diagnostic, placement, achievement, and proficiency tests. Emphasizing the close relationship between vocabulary knowledge and overall language proficiency, this article serves as a practical guide for both language learners and educators, offering insights into effective vocabulary learning and assessment techniques.

Keywords: high and low-frequency words; vocabulary knowledge; vocabulary learning; vocabulary testing

Effective language learning hinges on vocabulary development. While grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation all matter, having a limited vocabulary can pose a more significant challenge than poor grammar. As Wilkins (1972) wisely put it, "without grammar, very little can be conveyed; without vocabulary, nothing can be conveyed" (p. 111). Vocabulary knowledge strongly correlates with reading, writing, overall language proficiency, and academic achievement (see Laufer et al., 2004; Milton, 2013; Schmitt, 2010). Therefore, when embarking on vocabulary acquisition, it is vital to set clear objectives for what to learn and how much.

Both language learners and teachers should have a clear understanding of which vocabulary to prioritize, which aspects of vocabulary knowledge to emphasize, how to effectively learn or teach these aspects, and how to assess progress. This study aims to fill that void, offering English language learners and teachers a guide to enhance vocabulary learning and teaching.

It is important to note that words can be categorized into 1,000 frequency levels, often referred to as word families, denoted as K1, K2, K3, and so on. Nation (2006, 2022) classifies vocabulary from the British National Corpus (BNC) into twenty 1,000-word frequency levels.

These categories include proper nounsⁱ, marginal wordsⁱⁱ, compoundsⁱⁱⁱ, and a group of words not listed in these categories (Off-list). The BNC is a vast collection of 100 million words, comprising written and spoken language samples from various sources. It serves as a representative cross-section of British English, encompassing both spoken and written forms, spanning the late twentieth century (BNC official website, 2022).

Research based on word frequency highlights that some words are notably more valuable than others (refer to Schmitt, 2008; Laufer & Ravenhorst-Kalovski, 2010, and Schmitt & Schmitt, 2014). Therefore, when defining vocabulary learning objectives, the most effective strategy is to focus on mastering the most frequent words (Nation, 2022). An analysis of the texts and conversations learners are likely to encounter reveals that a thoughtfully selected set of words can significantly improve their comprehension. By examining various text types using 1,000 word-family lists from the BNC, Nation (2006) found that approximately 3,000 to 4,000 word families cover 95 percent of the text's content, while 6,000 to 9,000 word families are necessary to encompass 98 percent (see Table 1). The 98 percent coverage standard is backed by research (Hu & Nation, 2000; Schmitt et al., 2011; van Zeeland & Schmitt, 2013) and represents a manageable amount of unfamiliar vocabulary.

Table 1
English vocabulary sizes needed to get 95 and 98 percent coverage (including proper nouns) of various kinds of texts

Texts	95% coverage	98% coverage	Proper nouns
Novels	4,000 word families	9,000 word families	1–2%
Newspapers	4,000 word families	8,000 word families	5–6%
Children’s movies	4,000 word families	6,000 word families	1.5%
Spoken English	3,000 word families	7,000 word families	1.3%

Source: *Learning vocabulary in another language*, Nation (2022, p.16)

Word types

Vocabulary can effectively be categorized into three tiers based on frequency levels. These tiers include high-frequency words (comprising the most frequent 3,000 word families), mid-frequency words (including 6,000 word families from the fourth to the ninth 1,000 categories), and low-frequency words (including the tenth 1,000 and beyond). Nation and Coxhead (2021) utilize the metaphor of a tree to depict the expansion of vocabulary in native speakers. In this analogy, the roots symbolize the high-frequency words, the trunk represents the mid-frequency words, and the branches encompass the low-frequency words, which include specialized technical terms and vocabulary linked to specific professions or interests.

High-frequency words

High-frequency words encompass function words like 'it,' 'for,' 'and,' 'the,' and numerous content words such as 'tall,' 'blue,' 'computer,' 'nervously,' and 'drive.' Nation (2022) asserts that

approximately 80 percent of text words are high-frequency. Schmitt and Schmitt (2014) suggest adopting a high-frequency vocabulary of 3,000 word families. Combined with proper nouns, transparent compounds^{iv}, and marginal words, this typically covers about 95 percent of text (Nation, 2006).

Several valuable and thoughtfully curated high-frequency word lists are available, and using any of them ensures targeted learning of essential vocabulary. These lists include options such as the top 3,000 word families from Nation's BNC/COCA^v lists (2020), which are the most well-researched high-frequency word lists (Dang & Webb, 2014; Dang et al., 2020), Browne's (2014) New General Service List, Brezina and Gablasova's (2015) New General Service List, and Michael West's (1953) General Service List which is a classic high-frequency word list with around 2,000 word families.

Adopting any of these lists offers a concentrated method for becoming proficient in the most practically useful vocabulary. However, it is advisable to focus on mastering Nation's BNC/COCA lists (2020) as they are widely recognized as the most thoroughly researched high-frequency word lists (Dang & Webb, 2014; Dang et al., 2020). These word lists are accessible in [Paul Nation's resources](#). To effectively acquire these word lists, delving into the "4000 Essential English Words" book series (volumes 1 to 3), second edition, authored by Paul Nation, is a highly recommended approach.

Mid-frequency words

The second category consists of mid-frequency words, totaling 6,000 entries within the BNC/COCA lists, spanning from the fourth 1,000 to the ninth 1,000 words. These words are generally practical and moderately frequent, with many coming close to being classified as high-frequency. They are distinguished from low-frequency words by their role in forming essential vocabulary for independent English usage (Nation, 2022). Additionally, these words are primarily versatile and all-purpose. Mid-frequency word lists are accessible on [Paul Nation's website](#).

Differentiating between mid-frequency and low-frequency words is beneficial, as research indicates that approximately 6,000 to 9,000 words, when combined with proper nouns, cover around 98 percent of text (Nation, 2006). The top 9,000 most frequent words are likely to be equally important for understanding both spoken and written content. Notably, these words exhibit consistency across various text types, such as conversations, narratives, general explanations, or scholarly writing, as highlighted by Sorell (2013). Therefore, recognizing the core English vocabulary as comprising both high-frequency and mid-frequency words is advocated.

Low-frequency words

Low-frequency words are those that go beyond the most common 9,000 English words. According to Nation (2022), excluding proper nouns and using the BNC/COCA word list's Level-6 word-family definition^{vi} while considering specialized vocabulary provides an approximate estimate of around 40,000 word families for low-frequency words in English. When combined with high and mid-frequency words, the total comes to approximately 50,000 word families in the English language. It is worth noting that a significant portion of low-frequency

words includes proper names. Some low-frequency words are inherently uncommon, marked as archaic, highly formal, linked to specific dialects, considered impolite, or foreign loanwords.

Teachers should focus on instructing low-frequency words when they are essential for text comprehension or relevant within a specialized technical context. On the other hand, learners have the choice to learn low-frequency words deliberately, but it is often more effective to acquire them mainly through incidental exposure during reading and listening activities. It is important to note that a vast number of words, including mid-frequency and low-frequency words, will constitute a relatively minor portion of the instances in a given text. While these words ultimately need to be learned, their sheer volume means that the responsibility for learning them should primarily rest with the learners themselves (Nation, 2022).

Academic words

For language learners focusing on English for academic purposes, academic vocabulary represents a form of high-frequency vocabulary. Therefore, dedicating time to its acquisition is a valuable effort. Productively using academic vocabulary, both in writing and speaking, plays a significant role in achieving academic success.

Academic texts commonly feature words that are prevalent across various academic content, typically making up about 9 percent of the total words in the text (Nation, 2022). The Academic Word List (AWL), developed by Coxhead (2000), replaced the University Word List (Xue & Nation, 1984). Coxhead envisioned the AWL as the next step for learners after mastering high-frequency words and designed it accordingly.

Gardner and Davies (2014) introduced a new list of Academic Vocabulary List (AVL) by analyzing a comprehensive tagged academic corpus from the COCA. To facilitate a comparison with Coxhead's AWL, Gardner and Davies crafted a 570-word family version of their list. In all the comparative assessments conducted, their AVL consistently demonstrated broader coverage when compared to the AWL. The word lists for both AVL and AWL are accessible on the [EAP Foundation website](#) under the Vocab tab.

Nation (2022) examines the AWL and AVL, revealing they have about 200 common word families, comprising 211 word types and 192 word families. Learning from both lists is advantageous as they contain valuable vocabulary. However, as Nation emphasizes, Coxhead's AWL may introduce more unfamiliar terms to those not accustomed to academic content. The AWL is especially useful for learners with immediate academic objectives. To master it, consider studying "Focus on Vocabulary 2: Mastering the Academic Word List" by Diana and Norbert Schmitt or "4000 Essential English Words" book series (volume 4), second edition, authored by Paul Nation.

Interest in establishing an academic spoken word list has emerged. To address this, Dang, Coxhead, and Webb (2017) developed an Academic Spoken Word List, using a corpus gathered from various academic settings, including lectures, seminars, labs, and tutorials. The corpus was divided into four equally sized disciplinary sub-corpora, encompassing six diverse subject areas each, for a total of 24 subject areas under analysis. The Academic Spoken Word List is accessible on [Stuart Webb's website](#).

Technical (specialized) words

Beyond the realms of high-frequency and mid-frequency words in a language, individuals expand their vocabulary through their professions, interests, and areas of expertise. Technical vocabulary relevant to personal interests holds significance for those passionate about a subject. However, these terms may appear as infrequently encountered words to those unfamiliar with the field. Technical words are closely tied to the subject matter of a specific field and can be identified by consulting experts within that domain.

Technical words typically make up a significant portion of words in a text, ranging from one subject domain to another. The nature of technical vocabulary varies depending on the field of study, and technical words can include high-frequency, mid-frequency, or even low-frequency words, depending on context. Nation (2022) asserts that in some texts, technical words can account for 20 to 30 percent of the total words, and additionally, words from the AWL can function as technical vocabulary in specific texts.

The reason for distinguishing technical vocabulary from other forms of vocabulary is similar to distinguishing academic vocabulary from general-service words. The goal is to isolate a set of words that will be particularly useful for learners with specific language goals, such as understanding academic texts in a particular field, writing technical reports, or engaging in subject-specific discussions and conferences.

Vocabulary knowledge

Nation (2022) asserts that vocabulary knowledge can be dissected into four interrelated elements: (1) size or breadth, signifying the number of words one has command over, (2) depth, encapsulating the comprehensive understanding of diverse aspects associated with knowing a word, (3) strength, encompassing the degree of proficiency, including fluency and systematic comprehension, for each aspect, and (4) integration, evaluating the effectiveness with which knowledge of distinct words is interconnected. Competence in practical application materializes from these four constituents. Nation believes that receptive and productive knowledge is placed along a continuous spectrum, applicable across all these four elements of vocabulary knowledge.

In other words, vocabulary knowledge advances by increasing the number of known words (size), growing the strength of knowledge of each word (strength), including various aspects of word knowledge (depth), and fostering the integration of word knowledge in a word by constructing knowledge systems and by augmenting and organizing connections between individual words (integration).

Knowing a word

Nation (2022) highlights that words are not isolated units in a language; they fit into various related systems and levels. Consequently, there are many aspects to know about any given word and varying degrees of knowing. Nation identifies a broad range of aspects of word knowledge and provides a table illustrating what is involved in knowing a word. The table divides each item into receptive and productive knowledge. In essence, he suggests that receptive vocabulary use involves understanding the form of a word while listening or reading and retrieving its meaning,

while productive vocabulary use involves expressing meaning through speaking or writing and retrieving and using the appropriate spoken or written word form. He also asserts that these two terms apply to various aspects of language knowledge and use. However, when applied to vocabulary, these two terms encompass all 18 items mentioned in the following table.

Table 2
What is Involved in Knowing a Word

Form	Spoken	R	1. What does the word sound like?
		P	2. How is the word pronounced?
	Written	R	3. What does the word look like?
		P	4. How is the word written and spelled?
	Word parts	R	5. What parts are recognizable in this word?
		P	6. What word parts are needed to express the meaning?
Meaning	Form and meaning	R	7. What meaning does this word form signal?
		P	8. What form can be used to express this meaning?
	Concepts and referents	R	9. What is included in the concept?
		P	10. What items can the concept refer to?
	Associations	R	11. What other words does this make us think of?
		P	12. What other words could be used instead of this one?
Use	Grammatical functions	R	13. In what patterns does the word occur?
		P	14. In what patterns must we use this word?
	Collocations	R	15. What words or type of words occur with this one?
		P	16. What words or types of words must we use with this one?
	Constraints on use	R	17. Where, when and how often would we expect to meet this word?
		P	18. Where, when, and how often can we use this word?

Note: R = receptive knowledge, P = productive knowledge

Source: Learning vocabulary in another language, Nation (2022, p. 54)

Therefore, knowing a word involves various aspects of vocabulary knowledge from both receptive and productive perspectives. Here is a breakdown of these aspects:

Receptive Knowledge:

1. Recognizing the word's pronunciation and sound.
2. Familiarity with its written form.
3. Recognizing word parts (prefix, stem, suffix) and understanding their contribution to meaning.
4. Knowing the core common meaning of the word.
5. Understanding the word's meaning in specific contexts, and grasping the concept represented by the word, allowing for comprehension in various contexts.
6. Recognizing related words and associations.
7. Identifying correct usage in sentences.
8. Recognizing typical collocations or words used together with the word.
9. Awareness of the word's commonness and connotations.

Productive Knowledge:

1. Correctly pronouncing the word with appropriate stress.
2. Spelling and writing the word correctly.
3. Constructing the word using the correct word parts in their appropriate forms.
4. Producing the word to express the meaning.
5. Using the word in different contexts to convey various meanings.
6. Producing synonyms and opposites for the word.
7. Using the word correctly in original sentences.
8. Producing words that commonly co-occur with the word.
9. Making decisions regarding the word's formality and appropriateness in different situations.

These aspects encompass both receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge, providing a comprehensive understanding of what it means to know a word from both listening/reading and speaking/writing perspectives.

Teaching and learning vocabulary

Nation (2022) believes that the role of vocabulary teaching remains confined within a restricted scope in the process of vocabulary learning, comprising no more than a quarter of one of the four strands of a course (meaning-focused input, meaning-focused output, language-focused learning, and fluency development, see Nation, 2007). Teachers must exercise caution to avoid overemphasizing this role to the detriment of the time allocated for deliberate and incidental vocabulary learning.

Nation emphasizes that a teacher's responsibilities include planning, organization, training, testing, and instruction. Planning involves focusing on essential vocabulary and maintaining balance among four strands: meaning-focused input, meaning-focused output, language-focused learning, and fluency development. Organizational duties encompass executing activities like extensive reading, listening, spoken interactions, writing, fluency development, and learning exercises such as flashcards, intensive reading, and strategy training. Training helps learners take responsibility for their learning using effective strategies and principles. Testing involves tracking vocabulary progress and using assessments to promote learning. Lastly, Nation asserts that teaching, while important, is not as crucial as other roles, and he discusses three vital considerations for direct vocabulary instruction in language learning.

First, instruction should primarily target the high-frequency vocabulary of the language, and that includes the AWL for learners aiming at academic pursuits. The benefits of knowing high-frequency words justify the time spent on direct vocabulary instruction. Second, direct vocabulary instruction is just one component of a comprehensive course. It should occupy a limited portion of the overall course duration. Third, while direct instruction is effective for certain aspects of word knowledge, some aspects rely on experience and implicit knowledge rather than explicit teaching, making other methods more effective.

Certain evidence suggests that as vocabulary size expands, the depth of vocabulary knowledge also grows (Qian, 1999). Nation (2022) believes that one interpretation of this observation is that heightened interaction with a language not only facilitates the learning of new words but also reinforces and enhances the understanding of words previously encountered but only partially understood. If valid, this viewpoint implies that direct teaching and intentional

learning could be viewed as offering a rapid and efficacious enhancement in word knowledge, particularly pertaining to word form and meaning. Subsequent incidental learning could then work to bridge the numerous gaps in understanding and usage of that word.

Consequently, instructors should set modest objectives for vocabulary instruction, concentrating solely on high-frequency words, emphasizing the most important aspects of word knowledge, and allocating minimal time to each individual word. An essential aspect to consider when assessing the significance of direct vocabulary instruction is the connection between the knowledge acquired through direct instruction and the subsequent incidental learning via the meaning-focused and fluency strands of a course (Nation, 2022).

Vocabulary activities and procedures

Table 3 classifies vocabulary activities according to the various aspects involved in knowing a word, as outlined in Table 2. Multiple aspects of a word's knowledge should be addressed in comprehensive instruction.

Table 3
A range of activities for vocabulary learning

	spoken form	Pronouncing the words Developing phonological awareness Reading aloud
form	written form	Word and sentence dictation Finding spelling rules
	word parts	Filling word part tables Cutting up complex words Building complex words Choosing a correct form Finding etymologies
	form–meaning connection	Using word cards Using the keyword technique Matching words and definitions Discussing the meanings of phrases Drawing and labelling pictures Peer teaching Riddles True/False statements Reading with glosses
meaning	concept and reference	Finding common meanings Choosing the right meaning Semantic feature analysis Answering questions involving target words
	associations	Word detectives Finding substitutes Explaining connections Making word maps Classifying words Finding opposites Suggesting causes or effects Suggesting associations Finding examples
	grammar	Matching sentence halves Putting words in order to make sentences
use	collocates	Matching collocates Finding collocates Analysing and classifying collocates
	constraints on use	Identifying constraints Classifying constraints

Source: Learning vocabulary in another language, Nation (2022, p. 134)

Each individual aspect serves as the learning objective for the respective activity. Certain activities may encompass multiple aspects of word knowledge. Additional details regarding these activities can be found in Nation (2022) on pages 133-143.

It is crucial to acknowledge that word learning is a cumulative process (Swanborn & de Glopper, 1999). This means that unless there is an exceptional scenario where a word in a second language closely resembles one in the first language, we should anticipate that understanding a word happens incrementally over multiple spaced encounters. Even with substantial deliberate instruction, a single exposure does not lead to full word comprehension. Therefore, we should expect limited learning from a single encounter, and this understanding should inform our approach when planning or conducting such encounters.

Learning vocabulary out of class

There are three contexts for vocabulary learning, all of which can occur outside the classroom setting. The contexts are as follows:

- Extramural English or Extramural Learning (Sundqvist & Sylvén, 2016) involves unintentional learning through entertainment, such as watching TV or movies, browsing the Internet, online social interactions, playing digital games, listening to music, and leisurely digital reading or listening. It may also include interactions with native speakers and operates independently of a formal English course.
- Extra-Curricular Learning (Benson, 2011) happens beyond the classroom but is related to classroom courses. It is often guided by the classroom instructor but can also be initiated by learners to complement their classroom learning. Activities may include extensive reading, listening, interactions, writing, and deliberate vocabulary learning.
- Self-Directed Learning is where learners independently structure their language learning without a teacher's involvement, as illustrated in the case study by Nation and Yamamoto (2012) regarding autonomous Spanish learning.

Technology significantly expands vocabulary learning possibilities beyond the classroom, but it should be viewed as a tool rather than a magic solution. Learning through entertainment, such as gaming, social media, TV, movies, and songs, primarily involves incidental learning. For instance, consistent exposure to pop songs can facilitate the acquisition of a substantial portion of the 2,000 most frequent words. Vocabulary learning can occur during song listening, especially with repeated listening. Displaying song lyrics supports deliberate learning, and activities like karaoke or reading and singing song lyrics can enhance vocabulary acquisition (Pavia et al., 2019).

Graded readers and flashcards (word cards)

Deliberate vocabulary learning is highly efficient and productive. Courses that combine deliberate learning with incidental learning from communication-oriented tasks outperform those solely focused on incidental learning, particularly in terms of vocabulary acquisition speed (Vandenberghe et al., 2021).

Learning vocabulary deliberately before engaging in communication-driven tasks simplifies the complexity of these activities. Conversely, engaging in deliberate vocabulary learning after encountering words in communication tasks enhances the meaningfulness and motivation of such learning. Effective tools for deliberate vocabulary learning include graded readers and flashcards.

Graded readers are precisely crafted texts with a limited vocabulary, organized into different tiers. For instance, the Oxford Bookworms series by Oxford University Press offers six tiers ranging from 400 to 2,500 words. Learners with a vocabulary of under 400 words can comfortably read level one books, encountering only a few unfamiliar terms worth learning at that stage. Following Nation and Wang's (1999) recommendation, reading about five books at a specific level from the Oxford Bookworms series is beneficial. These graded readers primarily focus on high-frequency words, especially the 3,000 most frequent words. However, mid-frequency readers are designed for more advanced learners with vocabulary knowledge ranging from 4,000 to 8,000 words (Nation & Anthony, 2013). These readers can be found on [Paul Nation's website](#). More free graded readers can also be found at [Free Graded Readers](#).

Flashcards, also known as word cards, consist of cards with the target word in the second language (L2) on one side and its meaning, typically in the learner's first language (L1), an L2 synonym, or a definition on the other side. Modern flashcard apps like [Anki](#) and [Quizlet](#) offer multiple benefits over traditional paper cards. They allow progress tracking, customization of card presentation timing and frequency, and the inclusion of multimedia elements like images and audio to enhance learning. These applications are widely used for computer-assisted vocabulary learning (Nakata, 2011). Learners can create their own flashcard sets or access pre-made sets for various languages and subjects, making them a preferred choice for many.

Vocabulary testing

Nation (2022) provides valuable insights into the various purposes of language tests within language education. These assessments serve the following key roles:

- Diagnostic tests: These assessments pinpoint specific areas where learners face challenges, enabling educators to provide targeted interventions. This process may involve evaluating the effectiveness of vocabulary learning and coping strategies.
- Placement tests: These tests play a crucial role in appropriately assigning learners to proficiency levels or classes that align with their language skills.
- Short-term achievement tests: These evaluations help determine if a recently studied set of words has been successfully acquired over a brief period.
- Long-term achievement tests: These assessments evaluate the effectiveness of a course in teaching specific vocabulary over an extended duration, providing insights into sustained learning progress.
- Proficiency tests: These assessments gauge the extent of a learner's vocabulary knowledge and overall language proficiency.

The primary distinction among these test types lies in the selection of appropriate vocabulary. However, during test administration, the critical difference lies in how test results are interpreted and utilized for various educational purposes.

Diagnostic/placement tests

A diagnostic test plays a crucial role in helping teachers and learners make informed decisions about the appropriate course of action. It allows teachers to assess whether learners have an adequate vocabulary for specific tasks. One widely used diagnostic test is the Vocabulary Levels Test (VLT), which stands out for its versatility. The VLT is considered a diagnostic test since it shows in which word levels (1,000 to 5,000 and academic words in updated versions) the test takers may lack form-meaning knowledge. It comprises 24 to 30 items at each level, enabling selective administration to learners of various proficiency levels and providing reliable results.

Updated versions of the VLT, developed by McLean and Kramer (2015) and Webb, Sasao, and Ballance (2017), focus on evaluating the acquisition of high-frequency and valuable mid-frequency words (1,000 to 5,000 and AWL word levels in the former and 1,000 to 5,000 word levels only in the latter). These tests are conveniently accessible through [Paul Nation's repository](#). The online version of the VLT by Webb, Sasao, and Ballance (2017) is available at [Stuart Webb's repository](#).

For low-proficiency EFL learners, the VLT can serve as an effective placement measure. Meanwhile, the Vocabulary Size Test (VST) or its bilingual versions are more suitable for advanced learners. The VST, developed by Beglar (2010) and Nation & Beglar (2007), is specifically designed to measure a learner's overall vocabulary size. The VST comes in two versions of 14,000 and 20,000 word levels. A 14,000-word version consists of 140 multiple-choice items, with 10 items from each 1,000-word family level. To determine a learner's total receptive vocabulary size, their total score should be multiplied by 100. There are also two more recent parallel 20,000-word versions, each comprising 100 multiple-choice items. To calculate a learner's total receptive vocabulary size for these versions, their total score should be multiplied by 200. These two forms have been tested for their equivalence, ensuring their reliability and consistency.

The VST and its various bilingual versions can be accessed via [Paul Nation's resource site](#). Additionally, an [online VST version](#) is available. It is important to note that the VST, with

its multiple-choice format, might lead to excessive guessing by less proficient learners, as observed by Stoeckel, McLean, and Nation (2020) and is not suitable for them.

Achievement tests

Short-term achievement tests focus on recently studied words, typically over the past week or two, drawn directly from course materials. These tests offer feedback to both teachers and learners on the success of recent learning efforts. They do not gauge overall vocabulary size or guide future learning but serve as a prompt assessment tool.

According to Nation (2022), short-term achievement tests should possess specific characteristics: Ease of Creation (for simplicity in test generation), Ease of Grading (to provide quick feedback to learners), and Fairness (to align with recent course content and not overwhelm learners with too many expectations for a limited learning time). Examples of such tests can be found in Nation's book, notably on page 475.

Long-term achievement tests are usually administered at a course's end, with mid-course tests in longer courses to track progress. When selecting words for long-term achievement tests, the teacher should consider their intended purpose, typically grading and course evaluation. These tests should draw from the course's covered vocabulary, providing a reasonable representation of words encountered throughout the course. One approach is to select words from each week's lessons or units of study.

Test formats

Selecting the most suitable vocabulary test involves considering its intended purpose, the specific type of knowledge it aims to assess, the characteristics of the learners, and the circumstances in which it will be used. After a thorough evaluation of these factors, test creators can make informed decisions regarding vocabulary test formats and develop an approach to generate a representative sample of words for testing, striving to create an optimal vocabulary assessment.

A well-designed vocabulary test should utilize test-item formats that align with the specific aspects of vocabulary knowledge aimed to assess. Additionally, it should be straightforward to create, evaluate, and interpret the results. Having an ample number of test items is important for the test's reliability, with a minimum of around 30 items often recommended for a reliable assessment (Beglar & Hunt, 1999).

Nation (2022) suggests that when designing a vocabulary test, it is crucial to consider: which aspects of vocabulary knowledge to assess (depth), what strength of knowledge to assess and whether to give credit for partial knowledge or require full knowledge for credit (strength), and the amount of time and effort allocated to test creation and scoring. By carefully considering these factors, a vocabulary test that aligns with some specific goals and constraints can be designed. The following explores these three points.

What aspects of knowledge to test

The following table is an adapted version of Table 2, which outlines what is involved in knowing a word (depth of vocabulary knowledge). This table examines the aspects of knowledge to be measured in a test.

Table 4
Aspects of word knowledge for testing

Form	Spoken	R	Can the learner recognize the spoken form of the word?
		P	Can the learner pronounce the word correctly?
	Written	R	Can the learner recognize the written form of the word?
		P	Can the learner spell and write the word?
	Word parts	R	Can the learner recognize known parts in the word?
		P	Can the learner produce appropriate inflected and derived forms of the word?
Meaning	Form and meaning	R	Can the learner recall the appropriate meaning for this word form?
		P	Can the learner produce the appropriate word form to express this meaning?
	Concepts and referents	R	Can the learner understand a range of uses of the word and its central concept?
		P	Can the learner use the word to refer to a range of items?
	Associations	R	Can the learner produce common associations for this word?
		P	Can the learner recall this word when presented with related ideas?
Use	Grammatical functions	R	Can the learner recognize correct uses of the word in context?
		P	Can the learner use this word in the correct grammatical patterns?
	Collocations	R	Can the learner recognize appropriate collocations?
		P	Can the learner produce the word with appropriate collocations?
	Constraints on use	R	Can the learner tell if the word is common, formal, infrequent, etc?
		P	Can the learner use the word at appropriate times?

Note: R = receptive knowledge, P = productive knowledge
Source: Learning vocabulary in another language, Nation (2022, p. 481)

The table clearly illustrates the importance of considering various aspects beyond just the meaning of a word when evaluating learners' vocabulary knowledge. Nation (2022) also discusses how each of these aspects can be effectively tested. The following test item types are based on the table.

Spoken form

- Word or sentence dictation/ hear the word and choose the L1 translation
- Reading aloud/ cued oral recall

Written form

- Say these written words/say these regularly spelled nonsense words.
- Word or sentence dictation

Word parts

- Break the word into parts/choose or provide the meanings of the parts.
- Provide an affixed form of a known word.

Form and meaning

- Translate these words into L1/choose the right picture.
- Translate these words into L2.

Concept and referents

- Translate the underlined words into L1. 'It was a hard frost.'
- Choose the words to translate this L1 word

Associations

- Choose the words that you associate with this word
- Add to this list of associated words

Grammatical functions

- Is this sentence correct?
- Use this word in a sentence

Collocations

- Is this sentence correct?
- Produce collocations to go with this word

Constraints

- Which of these words represent UK use?
- What is the formal word for X?

(p. 499)

What strength of knowledge to test

Productive vocabulary knowledge, involving the ability to recall and use words actively, is generally more challenging and typically develops at higher levels of language learning (Laufer et al., 2004; Nation, 1990; Schmitt, 2010). Consequently, receptive knowledge tests, where learners identify word meanings or forms, are usually easier than productive knowledge tests, which require recall and word production from memory (Nation, 2022). Receptive tests align with understanding and recognition, which are often more accessible than active recall and production. Considering the ease of test items allows teachers to design assessments that effectively evaluate learners' vocabulary knowledge while creating a positive and encouraging learning environment.

Consequently, Nation (2022) asserts that test items should be easy so that learners are encouraged, teachers can observe if learners are progressing in the gradual cumulative learning of some specific words, and they can see if there are even small amounts of knowledge that can be built on. Vocabulary tests often employ recognition-based (receptive) formats, such as multiple-choice questions, because they tend to be easier for learners.

How much effort to make and mark the test

Tests used for significant decisions and future use require substantial effort in their creation. Conversely, tests designed to foster learning or provide short-term feedback, with minimal prospects of reuse, demand less investment. While formats like multiple-choice and matching can be labor-intensive to develop, translation tests (e.g. for the purpose of evaluating form-meaning connection) are relatively simpler, assuming learners share the same native language

(L1) (Nation, 2022). For vocabulary test items, in particular, they can often be reused, making some initial effort a wise investment for future use. Despite requiring more time to create, complex test items can often streamline the grading process, with multiple-choice tests serving as a prime example of this efficiency.

Using translations in tests

Nation (2022) argues that using the first language in vocabulary testing has a key advantage: it allows learners to respond to vocabulary items without relying on unrelated second language knowledge. For example, learners may struggle to explain word meanings in their second language during vocabulary interviews, as this requires advanced skills. Differentiating between a learner's uncertainty due to unfamiliarity with a word and difficulty defining it in the second language can be tricky.

Using the first language's meaning is like using a simple synonym. In contrast, providing a definition in the second language often requires a more complex grammatical structure, such as a relative clause, demanding higher grammatical proficiency for comprehension. Using first language translations is a valuable approach for assessing vocabulary, covering receptive and productive aspects, as well as recall and recognition tasks (Nation, 2022). Nation emphasizes that challenges arising from imprecise equivalences between the first language (L1) and second language (L2) meanings are likely less problematic than issues arising from mismatches between an L2 definition and the intended meaning.

Final thoughts on vocabulary testing

Tests can encompass vocabulary that learners intentionally and consciously recall. These tests primarily assess declarative knowledge, which is the knowledge that learners can articulate and explain (form-meaning link). However, the ultimate goal should be to evaluate procedural knowledge, which is the learners' capacity to effectively use words in both receptive and productive contexts when their primary focus is on conveying or comprehending the message (Nation, 2022).

Vocabulary learning serves a functional purpose, aiming to enhance learners' abilities in listening, speaking, reading, or writing effectively. When assessing vocabulary, it is crucial to differentiate between the depth of one's understanding of a word and their practical use of the same word. This distinction allows educators to identify if a lack of vocabulary knowledge contributes to learners' difficulties in listening, speaking, reading, or writing tasks.

Conclusion

The current article has illuminated various aspects of vocabulary knowledge, delving into different vocabulary types and examining vocabulary acquisition and assessment. Vocabulary knowledge and language proficiency are closely intertwined, with an emphasis on how vocabulary knowledge enhances language proficiency. To address this, advocating for a balanced approach is essential, involving the combination of deliberate vocabulary instruction and spontaneous, incidental learning. In summary, the present article functions as a valuable asset for

individuals learning a language and for educators, providing valuable insights into the domain of vocabulary knowledge and effective techniques for learning and assessing vocabulary.

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Notes

ⁱ nouns that serve as the name for a specific place, person, or thing, such as London, Jim, Google

ⁱⁱ Exclamations, hesitations, and interjections (such as gee, oh well, gosh) that are common in spoken English but are marginal as words

ⁱⁱⁱ two or more words linked together to produce a word with a new meaning such as toothbrush, ecofriendly.

^{iv} Transparent compounds are those whose component parts (lexemes) are semantically related to the meaning of the entire word, such as snowball or doghouse

^v The British National Corpus (BNC) and the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA)

^{vi} Bauer and Nation (1993) model of the most useful word affixes, divided into basewords and six levels of affixation